

K-Protection of Global Secret in Discrete Event Systems Using Supervisor Control

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Abstract—This work addresses the security problem of protecting secrets in the framework of discrete event systems that are modeled by deterministic finite automata. We characterize a global secret that composes of one or multiple states, in which each state is assigned to a security level. A state is said to be protected if any event sequence from the initial state for reaching it contains the amount of protected events equal to or greater than the required security level. In addition, we assume that the protected event labels must be recovered within a bounded of consecutive protected events (called as K -protection). Our objective is to design a K -protection event policy such that the protected secret state pieces satisfy a predefined protection threshold. To this end, we first construct a security automaton that integrates the system state information and its current security level, and a K -protection automaton that lists all the possible protections of event sequences. Then by using the supervisor control theory technique, the valid protecting policy to enforce the security requirement is obtained. Finally, examples are used to illustrate the proposed protection method.

I. INTRODUCTION

Security and privacy problems of cyber physical systems have attracted much attention recently [1]–[3]. They mainly investigate the problem of opacity verification [4], supervisor control [5], [6], fault diagnosis [7], [8]. However, previous works primarily focus on permanent attack effects or continuous secret protection, which may not be practical due to cost considerations.

In this work, we focus on the problem of secret protection in discrete event systems modeled by deterministic finite automata. In reality, a secret means important information that cannot be accessed or deduced by the external users. To protect such states in different concepts, there mainly exist two parts, opacity [9]–[11] and secret protection [12], [13]. Opacity refers to a system property that prevents an external intruder from deducing a specific set of secrets through system observations, distinguishing it from the concept of secret protection. The latter involves actively safeguarding events to ensure security requirements, while opacity assumes that an intruder passively observes events

and infers secrets based on those observations. In order to keep secrets, it is essential to ensure that certain security measures, such as password checks and face ID recognition, are implemented when attempting to access crucial states or personal information. Essentially, an operational sequence that grants access to a secret state must include a series of protected events, which necessitate identity verification to pass security checks. Moreover, to maintain opacity, it is necessary for secret sequences to exhibit the same projection as non-secret sequences. Its enforcement usually needs to modify its sensor reading or edit event labels by using edit function or insert function [14], [15].

The first novelty of this work is to characterize a global secret that composes of one or several states, in which each state is associated with a security level. Motivated from the puzzle game, we know that a secret is usually hidden in several secret states, i.e., the final result or the total secret consists of several secret information parts. In general, even if not all the pieces are disclosed, it is possible to deduce the secret based on the majority of the revealed parts, depending on their importance. For instance, unlocking a mobile phone using face ID recognition while wearing a mask relies more heavily on the information from the eyes to reveal the secret. Secondly, from a practical viewpoint, we assume that after a bounded number of consecutive protected events, the protected event labels must be recovered, which leads to a new notion of K -protection. This setting is more practical due to the consideration of intermittent protection affect. This concept is inspired by the work presented in [16] that analyzes the robust diagnosis problem against the intermittent loss sensor observation.

Our objective is to design a K -protection event policy that ensures the existence of event sequences leading to secret pieces, containing the amount of protected events equal to or greater than the required security level, such that the protected secret pieces satisfy the given protection setting value. To do so, a security automaton that integrates the information of the system state and its current security level is given, and then a K -protection automaton that lists all the possible protections of event sequences is established. Then by using the supervisor control theory technique [17], the valid protecting policy for enforcing the security requirement is obtained.

The content of this paper is structured as follows. Section II introduces some basic concepts on automaton, recalls the supervisor control technique of discrete event systems. Section III characterizes the secret protection problem and formally gives the problem statement. In Section IV we de-

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This work is a part of the eCharge4Drivers project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 875131. This content reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information this publication contains.

sign the K -protection event policy. Finally, some conclusions and future works are presented in Section V.

II. PRELIMINARIES

Moreover, due to the space limit, only necessary notions used in Sections III and IV are given in the following, but the readers can refer to [9] and [18] for more details.

A. Deterministic finite automaton

Let Σ be a finite set of events and Σ^* denote the set of all finite length strings over Σ , including the empty string ε . The length of a string s is the number of events in s , denoted by $|s|$. A language $L \subseteq \Sigma^*$ is a subset of finite-length strings. A prefix of a string $s \in \Sigma^*$ is a string u such that there exists a string v satisfying $uv = s$, in which uv represents the concatenation of two strings u and v . The prefix closure of s is the set of all its prefixes, given by the set $\bar{s} = \{u \in \Sigma^* \mid \exists v \in \Sigma^*, uv = s\}$.

A deterministic finite automaton (DFA) $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$ is used to model a DES, where Q is a set of states, Σ is a set of events, $f : Q \times \Sigma \rightarrow Q$ is the partial transition function, and $q_0 \in Q$ is the initial state. The transition function f can be extended to $Q \times \Sigma^* \rightarrow Q$ in the usual manner: $f(q, \sigma u) = f(f(q, \sigma), u)$ for $q \in Q$, $\sigma \in \Sigma$, and $u \in \Sigma^*$. Note that $f(q, \varepsilon) = q$ and $f(q, \sigma u)$ is undefined if $f(q, \sigma)$ is undefined. The generated language of DFA G , denoted by $L(G)$, is defined as $L(G) = \{u \in \Sigma^* \mid f(q, u) \text{ is defined}\}$.

B. Supervisory control

For a DFA $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$, the event set Σ is divided into two disjoint subsets $\Sigma = \Sigma_c \cup \Sigma_{uc}$, where Σ_c (resp., Σ_{uc}) is the set of controllable events (resp., uncontrollable events).

A language specification is given by a regular language $W \subseteq \Sigma^*$. By dynamically disabling events of the system, a supervisor S restricts the system G with respect to the specification W . A supervisor S implements simultaneously with the system and, i.e., once an event sequence $s \in L(G)$ is executed by the system, the supervisor outputs a control decision $\xi(s) \subseteq \Sigma_c$ to disable all controllable events not in $\xi(s)$. Particularly, any uncontrollable $\sigma \in \Sigma_{uc}$ cannot be disabled by a supervisor. In addition, a language W is controllable with respect to $L(G)$ if it holds the following statement

$$\overline{W}\Sigma_{uc} \cap L(G) \subseteq \overline{W}.$$

In cases that the language W is not controllable, we obtain a supervisor S by computing the supremal controllable sublanguage of $L(G)$ with respect to W ,

$$L(G)^{\uparrow W} = \bigcup \{Y \subseteq L(G) \mid Y \text{ is controllable to } L(G)\}$$

by iteratively manipulating regular languages.

For a state specification, it characterizes a set of illegal (or forbidden) states $Q_f \subseteq Q$ that can not reach any state in Q_f . Similarly, we design a supervisor S to enforce Q_f by converting the state specification Q_f into its equivalent language specification $W = \{s \in L(G) \mid f(q_0, s) \notin Q_f\}$. This could be obtained by computing the supremal controllable sublanguage of W .

III. SECRET PROTECTION AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

This work addresses the problem of secret protection in discrete event systems. we first characterize a global secret that is composed of one or several states in the system, in which each system state is assigned to a predefined security level. Then we give a condition to determine whether a global secret is protected. To explore the occurrence of intermittent protection phenomenon, we introduce a new notion known as K -protection for the global secret. Finally, we formalize the problem statement.

A. Secret protection

Given a system $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$, specific events are considered protectable, signifying that they can undergo security checks such as password verification or face ID recognition. By assumption, we divide the set of events Σ into the sets of protectable events Σ_p and unprotectable events Σ_{np} with $\Sigma = \Sigma_p \cup \Sigma_{np}$. In practice, certain states known as secret pieces hold personal confidential information and can be accessed from the system's entry point through specific security checks.

Definition 3.1 (Security requirement [12]): Given a system $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$, we define a security requirement as a function $l : Q \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ where each state $q \in Q$ is assigned to a security level. $l(q)$ represents the minimum number of protected events required to reach q from initial state q_0 . \diamond

In this work, all states of systems containing positive security levels are considered as *secret state pieces* (secret state for short), which is denoted by a subset of states $Q_S = \{q \in Q \mid l(q) > 0\}$. Inspired from the puzzle game, we know that a global secret is usually hidden in several secret states, i.e., the final result or the global secret consists of several important information parts. In general, even not all the pieces are disclosed, it is possible to deduce the secret based on the majority of the revealed parts, depending on their importance. The following definition characterizes a global secret of a system.

Definition 3.2 (Global secret): Given a set of secret states Q_S and the security requirement l , a global secret (secret for short) is composed of a subset of secret states $Q'_S \subseteq Q_S$, in which each secret state $q_j \in Q'_S$ is associated with its weight $w_j = \frac{l(q_j)}{\sum_{q_i \in Q'_S} l(q_i)}$. \diamond

In this work, we only consider the case that all the secret states compose a global secret only, i.e., $Q'_S = Q_S$, and we assume that a global secret is protected if it satisfies:

$$\sum_{\forall q_k \in Q_S} w_k \geq \delta, q_k \text{ is protected} \quad (1)$$

where the state q_k is said to be protected if any sequence from initial state to q_k has at least $l(q_k)$ protected events, and δ is a user-defined value that could be set up according to the different cases. For simplicity, we assume $\delta = 0.5$ in the reminder of this work.

Example 1: Consider the system $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$ shown in Fig. 1, the initial state is q_0 . An intruder or a regular user can establish a connection with the server using event σ_1 .

Starting from state q_1 , the user has two possible paths to access account information: via event σ_3 to reach state q_3 for general personal information access, and via events σ_2 and σ_4 to reach state q_4 for accessing crucial information such as credit card numbers. We set the security level of state q_3 as 1 and state q_4 as 2 (i.e., $l(q_3) = 1$ and $l(q_4) = 2$) while the others are set to zero. This implies that accessing general personal information requires at least one security check, while accessing crucial information requires a minimum of two security checks.

We assume that protectable event set is $\Sigma_p = \{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_4\}$ and unprotectable event set is $\Sigma_{np} = \{\sigma_3\}$, and the set of secret states is $Q_S = \{q_3, q_4\}$. The global state is composed of two secret states and their weights are $w_3 = \frac{l(q_3)}{l(q_3)+l(q_4)} = \frac{1}{3}$, $w_4 = \frac{l(q_4)}{l(q_3)+l(q_4)} = \frac{2}{3}$, the higher weight w_4 means the secret state q_4 is more important inside the global secret. In a case that only event σ_1 is protected while the other is unprotected, such that $l(q_3) = 1$ holds and $l(q_4) = 2$ does not hold. In other words, secret state q_3 is protected and q_4 is unprotected, such that the sum of weight of protected secrets is $w_3 = 1/3$ that is lower than the threshold $\delta = 0.5$. Thus the secret (global secret) is not protected. \diamond

Fig. 1. System G and a global secret that composes of states q_3 and q_4 .

B. K -protection of a global secret

From a practical viewpoint, we assume that after a bounded number of consecutive protected events, the protected event labels must be recovered, which leads to a new notion of K -protection. More precisely, given a sequence $s \in \Sigma^*$, if the label $\sigma \in \Sigma$ have been protected $K \in \mathbb{N}$ times consecutively in s under the protection strategy, then their $(K + 1)$ th occurrence must be not protected. This setting is more practical due to the consideration of intermittent protection affect. The following example is used to illustrate a scenario about K -protection.

Example 2: Let us consider again the system in Example 1. Assume the system executes a sequence $s = \sigma_1\sigma_2\sigma_4$ and the maximum consecutive protection is $K = 1$, if the protected event is σ_1 , the following event σ_2 cannot be protected according to intermittent protection setting. In a case that the maximum consecutive protection is $K = 2$, if the protected events are σ_1 and σ_2 , then the following event σ_4 cannot be protected. \diamond

To distinguish whether the occurrence of an event $\sigma \in \Sigma_p$ is protected, we denote by σ^p and σ^{np} the event σ that is protected and is not protected, respectively. Let T_p be the

set of events that are protected, and T_{np} be the set of events that are not protected. Inspired from the approach in [16], to obtain all the possible protections of an event sequence, we define a replacement function $Re : \Sigma^* \rightarrow 2^{(T_p \cup T_{np})^*}$, where $Re(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon$, $Re(\sigma_i) = \{\sigma_i^p, \sigma_i^{np}\}$, if $\sigma_i \in \Sigma_p$, otherwise $Re(\sigma_i) = \sigma_i$. Moreover, $Re(\sigma t) = Re(\sigma)Re(t)$ for all $\sigma \in \Sigma$ and $t \in \Sigma^*$. In the following, we formally present K -protection in the considered DES.

Definition 3.3 (K -protection): Let $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$ be a DFA and $s \in \Sigma^*$ be a sequence. A function that models the intermittent protection, such that the maximum number of consecutive protected events is K , is a mapping

$$\Phi : \Sigma^* \rightarrow 2^{(T_p \cup T_{np})^*}$$

where a sequence $\sigma^+ \in \Phi(\sigma)$, if σ^+ satisfies the following conditions:

- (i) $\sigma^+ \in Re(\sigma)$;
- (ii) for all $\mu', \mu'' \in (T_p \cup T_{np})^*$ and $\mu''' \in T_p^*$, such that $\sigma^+ = \mu' \mu'' \mu'''$, then $|\mu''| \leq K$. \diamond

Condition (i) ensures that the sequence σ^+ is obtained from the replacement function $Re(\sigma)$. Condition (ii) guarantees that the maximum number of consecutive protection of s is K .

Example 3: Continue the Example 2, assume that the system executes a transition sequence $s = \sigma_1\sigma_2\sigma_4$ and $K = 1$, by Definition 3.3, it gets the following sequences since K -protection, $\Phi(s) = \{\sigma_1^p\sigma_2^{np}\sigma_4^{np}, \sigma_1^{np}\sigma_2^p\sigma_4^{np}, \sigma_1^{np}\sigma_2^{np}\sigma_4^p, \sigma_1^{np}\sigma_2^{np}\sigma_4^{np}\}$. \diamond

C. Problem statement

To uphold a security requirement l while meeting the specified protection threshold δ and maximum consecutive protection restriction K , our objective is to design an event protection policy v that determines the protected events for each generated sequence s within $L(G)$.

Definition 3.4: Consider a system $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$ and the maximum consecutive protection K , we define a protecting policy as a function $v : L(G) \times \Sigma_p \times k \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ with $0 \leq k \leq K$ upon the generation of sequence $s \in L(G)$, in which the event protection policy v ensures that the set of protected events following s is represented as $v(s) \subseteq \Sigma_p$. \diamond

With a slight modification in [12], given a protecting policy v , we define $v(s, \sigma, k) = 1$ (respectively, $v(s, \sigma, k) = 0$) if it has $k \leq K$ and $\sigma \in v(s)$ (respectively, $(\sigma \notin v(s)) \vee (k > K)$). From [12], a valid protecting policy v ensures that for any sequence s in $L(G)$, leading to a state $q \in Q$, the number of events protected by v in sequence s is equal to or exceeds the security level $l(q)$ corresponding to state q . However, this concept cannot be used in our approach directly since the consideration of the protection threshold δ and the maximum consecutive protection K . In the following, we characterize a valid protecting policy in our setting.

Definition 3.5: Consider a system $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$, a security requirement $l : Q \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, a secret protection threshold δ , a maximum consecutive protection K and a set of secret states Q_S . A protecting policy v is said to be valid if for

any sequence $s = \sigma_1 \cdots \sigma_n \in L(G)$, with $f(q_0, s) = q$ and $q \in Q_S$, such that it holds a subset of secret states $Q'_S \subseteq Q_S$ satisfying:

$$\begin{cases} \text{(i)} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} v(\bar{s}_i, \sigma_{i+1}, k) \geq l(q) & \forall q \in Q'_S \\ \text{(ii)} \sum_{\forall q \in Q'_S} l(q) \geq \delta \cdot \sum_{\forall q \in Q_S} l(q) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

◇

Example 4: Consider the Example 1 again with $\Sigma_p = \{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_4\}$, $\Sigma_{np} = \{\sigma_3\}$ and $Q_S = \{q_3, q_4\}$. Assume that a secret protection threshold $\delta = 0.5$, and the maximum consecutive protection $K = 1$. According to the protecting policy, $v(\varepsilon) = \sigma_1, v(\sigma_1) = \sigma_2, v(\sigma_1\sigma_2) = \sigma_4$, and $v(s) = \emptyset$ for all other sequences. A valid protecting policy is the following: a) $v(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, 1) = 0$ means that after sequence σ_1 and the number of consecutive protected events $k = 1$, according to Definition 3.5, its following event σ cannot be protected. Then the consecutive protection becomes $k = 0$. b) $v(\sigma_1\sigma_2, \sigma_3, 0) = 1$ means after sequence σ_1 and the number of consecutive protected events $k = 0 \leq K$, according to Definition 3.5, its following event σ_4 can be protected. Above all, to protect the global secret and satisfying the protection threshold δ and K , we could protect event σ_1 and σ_4 . ◇

In this work, the main objective is to address the following problem.

Problem 1: Given a system $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$ and a security requirement $l : Q \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, the maximum consecutive protection K and a secret protection threshold δ , our objective is to determine a valid protecting policy v .

More precisely, we need to establish an event protection policy that for a subset of secret states, any sequences starting from the initial state, which leads to a secret state while encompassing a sufficient number of protected events that meets or exceeds the required security level. Meanwhile, it holds that the protected secret states satisfy protection threshold value δ . In addition, we cannot protect all protectable events due to the intermittent protection setting (i.e., the existence of maximum consecutive protection K). Thus, the protecting policy satisfying such requirement is developed in the following parts.

IV. SECURITY AUTOMATA AND PROTECTING POLICY

In this section, we first recall a structure known as the security automaton, which encodes both the system behavior and the information regarding protection requirements. Then a K -protection automaton that lists all the possible protection of event sequences is established. Finally, by using supervisory control theory, we construct the system subject to K -protection and design a protecting policy that satisfies all the requirements.

A. Security automaton

Definition 4.1 ([12]): Let $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$ be a system and $l : Q \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ be a security requirement such that each state associated with a maximal security level is l . We define the security automaton (SA) of system G as a DFA $H = (Q_H, \Sigma_H, f_H, q_{0,0})$ satisfying:

- $Q_H = \{q_{i,h} \mid 0 \leq i \leq |Q|, 0 \leq h \leq l\}$ is a set of states;

- $\Sigma_H = T_p \cup T_{np}$ is a set of events with two duplicates of set Σ : $T_p = \{\sigma_1^p, \dots, \sigma_n^p\}$ and $T_{np} = \{\sigma_1^{np}, \dots, \sigma_n^{np}\}$;
- $q_{0,0}$ is the initial state;
- $f_H : Q_H \times \Sigma_H \rightarrow Q_H$ is the transition function such that $\forall f(q_i, \sigma_j^{np}) = q'_i$, it has that $f_H(q_{i,h}, \sigma_j^p) = q_{i',h}, \forall h = 0, \dots, l$; $f_H(q_{i,h}, \sigma_j^{np}) = q_{i',h+1}, \forall h \leq l-1$.

◇

Example 5: Consider the system in Fig. 1 with $l(q_3) = 1, l(q_4) = 2$, and $l(q) = 0$ for $q \neq q_3, q_4$. The corresponding partially SA H is shown in Fig. 2. Specifically, states $q_{0,1}$ and $q_{0,2}$ are eliminated since those two states cannot be reached. For a transition $f_H(q_{0,0}, \sigma_1^{np}) = q_{1,0}$, it implies that a state q_1 is reached from the initial state q_0 by executing an event σ_1 while σ_1 is not protected such that the security level remains its security level as zero. For a transition $f_H(q_{0,0}, \sigma_1^p) = q_{1,1}$, it holds that the current security level is increased from 0 to 1 by protecting the event σ_1 . As presented in Example 1, the event σ_3 is unprotectable, such that from state q_1 to reach a state q_3, σ_3^p cannot be used to update the state. ◇

Fig. 2. SA with $l(q_3) = 1$ and $l(q_4) = 2$.

From Example 3, we know that an SA encompasses the current state of the corresponding system and its security level. Additionally, an SA is able to present the evolution of a system with the valid protection policy v when intermittent protection is not considered. Precisely, let's assume that an SA evolves to state $q_{i,h}$, indicating that the system is in state q_i with a security level of h . Suppose that the system executes the next event σ_j , resulting in $f(q_i, \sigma_j) = q_k$.

- If event σ_j is protected by operator, denoted as σ_j^p , the state $q_{k,h+1}$ is reached by performing event σ_j^p . Consequently, the system reaches state q_k with an incremented security level of 1.
- If event σ_j is unprotected by operator, denoted as σ_j^{np} , the state $q_{k,h}$ is reached by performing event σ_j^{np} . As a result, the system evolves to state q_k without any change in the security level.

B. K -protection Automaton

Due to the consideration of the maximum consecutive protection K of a sequence, the previous proposed automaton cannot respect such requirement. In this part, we present an algorithm to build the K -protection automaton.

Algorithm 1: Construction of automaton Δ

Input: $K, \langle Q, \Sigma, f, q_0 \rangle, T_p, T_{np}$
Output: $\Delta = (Q_k, T_p \cup T_{np}, \delta', Q_0)$

- 1 Let $Q_0 = (\sigma^p, 0), Q_k = \emptyset, i = 0, j = 0;$
- 2 **while** $i \leq K$ **do**
- 3 $Q_k = Q_k \cup \{(\sigma^p, i)\};$
- 4 **for** $\sigma \in \Sigma$ **do**
- 5 **if** $\sigma \in \Sigma_p$ **then**
- 6 $Q_k = Q_k \cup \{(\sigma^p, i)\};$
- 7 $\delta'((\sigma^p, i), \sigma^p) = (\sigma^p, i + 1);$
- 8 $\delta'((\sigma^p, i), \sigma^{np}) = (\sigma^p, 0);$
- 9 **if** $\sigma \in \Sigma_{np}$ **then**
- 10 $\delta'((\sigma^p, i), \sigma) = (\sigma^p, i);$
- 11 $i = i + 1;$
- 12 **while** $j < K$ **do**
- 13 **for** $\sigma \in \Sigma_p$ **do**
- 14 $\delta'((\sigma^p, j), \sigma^p) = (\sigma^p, j + 1);$
- 15 $j = j + 1;$

Algorithm 2 lists all the possible protections of event sequences within K consecutive protection in the proposed K -protection automaton, where Q_K is the set of states, $T_p \cup T_{np}$ is the set of event labels, δ' is the transition relation, and Q_0 is the initial state. Each state of Q_K is a tuple formed by the occurrence of protected event $\sigma \in T_p$ and a counter with the number of protection of σ . In detail, line 1 initializes the state set, the initial state, and two indexes i, j . The initial state $Q_0 = (\sigma^p, 0)$ implies that the amount of consecutive corrupted observations σ^p is 0. In the lines 2–11, the occurrence of an event $\sigma \in \Sigma_p$ generates a new state (σ^p, i) and creates the transition from (σ^p, i) to state $(\sigma^p, i + 1)$, while the occurrence of an event $\sigma \in \Sigma_{np}$ remains in the state (σ^p, i) and creates the self-loop transition. In addition, if the occurrence of event is not protected, the occurrence of σ^{np} resets the counter as 0. Lines 12–15 presents that the occurrence of event σ^p increases the counter and creates the transition from state (σ^p, j) to state $(\sigma^p, j + 1)$. Consequently, the maximum number of consecutive occurrences of σ^p , without the occurrence of σ^{np} , is equal to K .

Example 6: Consider the system in Example 1 again and the maximum consecutive protection is $K = 2$, by using Algorithm 2, the K -protection automaton Δ is shown in Fig.3. Specifically, the state $(q_{4,3}, 3)$ cannot be reached from the state $(q_{2,2}, 2)$ by protecting the event σ_4 since the maximum consecutive protections in the event sequences must be less than $K = 2$. \diamond

The systems subject to K -protection can be constructed by the parallel composition of the automaton Δ and the security automaton, such that $H' = H \parallel \Delta$.

Example 7: Let us consider again the system in Example 1 and the maximum consecutive protection K is 2, the system subject to K -protection is displayed as shown in Fig. 4. Due to $K = 2$, thus the state $q_{4,3}, 3$ cannot exist under

Fig. 3. Automaton Δ of Example 3.

this setting, where three consecutive protected events occur.

Fig. 4. System G subject to K -protection.**C. Supervisory control for K -protection policy**

In this part, supervisory control problem with state specification in discrete-event systems is presented at first, and then the previous Problem 1 can be transformed into a supervisory control problem with respect to K -protection, such that an event-protecting policy could be obtained by inferring an algorithm.

Problem 2: Consider a system $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$ with the event partition $\Sigma = \Sigma_c \cup \Sigma_{uc}$ and a state specification Q_f characterizing a set of forbidden states, we design $\xi : L(G) \rightarrow 2^{\Sigma_c}$ such that G controlled by ξ does not reach any state in Q_f .

The acquisition of supervisor ξ has been well-established in the literature. Precisely, it is from system G by eliminating all states in $Q \setminus Q_f$ and all states that is reachable to $Q \setminus Q_f$ via uncontrollable sequences in Σ_{uc}^* . Hereafter, the forbidden state contains the state in H' that the current security level is lower than its required security level or its current consecutive protection is greater than its maximum one. By considering the approach in [12] and the maximum consecutive protection K restriction in this paper, its corresponding SCP-KSA is defined as follows.

Problem 3(SCP-KSA): Consider a system $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$ with a security requirement $l : Q \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, a secret protection threshold δ , a maximum consecutive protection K and a set of secret states Q_S , let $H = (Q_H, T_p \cup T_{np}, f_H, q_{0,0})$ be the corresponding SA. We aim to design a

supervisor ξ of $H' = H||\Delta$ with respect to

$$\begin{cases} \Sigma_c = \{\sigma_i^{np} \in T_{np} \mid \sigma_i \in \Sigma_p\} \\ \Sigma_{uc} = T_p \cup \{\sigma_i^{np} \in T_{np} \mid \sigma_i \in \Sigma_{np}\} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

a state specification $Q_f = \{(q_{i,h}, k) \mid h < l(q_i), k > K\}$ that encodes the state $q_{i,h}$ and the current consecutive protection k , and the sum of weight of protected secret state $\sum_{\forall q_k \in Q_s} \geq \delta$.

The secret protection problem gives rise to the corresponding SCP-KSA, which can be formulated as a supervisory control problem in the corresponding system. This system is derived by performing the parallel composition of SA and the K -protection automaton, such that i) the set of controllable events Σ_c includes all events σ_i^{np} in the event set T_{np} , and their associated events σ_i are protectable; ii) the set of uncontrollable events Σ_{uc} comprises all events σ_i^p in the event set T_p and all σ_i^{np} in T_{np} , and their associated events σ_i are unprotectable; and iii) the set of forbidden states contains all states $(q_{i,h}, k)$, where the security level h falls below the required level $l(q_i)$ and the current consecutive protected events k is greater than the maximum one K . It holds the duality between the solution of a secret protection problem and the solution of its corresponding SCP-KSA, thus we could only solve the solution of SCP-KSA to guarantee the valid protection policy. The following algorithm determines the K -protection policy.

Algorithm 2: Determine a K -protection policy to enforce the security requirement

Input: A system $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$ with $\Sigma = \Sigma_p \cup \Sigma_{np}$, a security requirement l , a secret protection threshold δ , a maximum consecutive protection K , a subset of secret states $Q_S \subseteq Q$

Output: K -protection policy

- 1 Construct the security automaton $H = (Q_H, \Sigma_H, f_H, q_{0,0})$ of G with the security requirement l ;
 - 2 Compute the K -protection automaton $\Delta = (Q_k, T_p \cup T_{np}, \delta', Q_0)$;
 - 3 Compute the automaton H' by parallel composition and then solve the SCP-KSA in H' by designing a supervisor ξ ;
 - 4 **if** ξ is empty **then**
 - 5 Output “no solution” and return;
 - 6 **else**
 - 7 Design the K -protection policy v ;
 - 8 Return v ;
-

Proposition 4.2: Given a system $G = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_0)$ with the event partition $\Sigma = \Sigma_p \cup \Sigma_{np}$, a security requirement $l : Q \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ and a protection threshold δ , a maximum consecutive protection K , let $H = (Q_H, \Sigma_H, f_H, q_{0,0})$ and $\Delta = (Q_k, T_p \cup T_{np}, \delta, Q_0)$ be the security automaton and K -protection automaton, respectively. The valid protecting policy with respect to $H' = H||\Delta$ that is determined by Algorithm 2 is feasible.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a global secret K -protection problem is investigated in the framework of discrete event systems. To solve the problem, two new structures called the security automaton and K -protection automaton have been established, such that the system subject to K -protection is constructed by using parallel composition technique. Then by applying the supervisory control with state specification, the event policy is obtained by the proposed algorithm. In future work, we will investigate the optimization problem of our proposed method

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